

Analysis of NEWSERA's communication strategies through the Kampal Social tool for the digital sphere

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the results of the analysis on Newsera using the Kampal Social tool (<https://social.kampal.com/>) in the framework of the H2020 European NEWSERA project. The digital indicators, corresponding to different social media and provided by Newsera, have been monitored and analysed. The results are presented for the period February 2022-February 2023, including the most relevant key ideas and conclusions based on the monthly monitoring carried out. Thus, the main findings, together with some recommendations, mostly correspond to 2022. The full set of results is shown in a dynamic way on the KAMPAL Social website - available on demand.

The analyses in this report are mainly on Twitter and also include results on YouTube. In the case of Twitter, the evolution of the main hashtags and the mentions and retweets received by the most important users can be seen. In relation to the general network of users and mentions among them, it is clear that there are different spaces or communities where the NEWSERA project is interacting: on the one hand, the analysis makes explicit the connections both with accounts of individuals, projects and institutions at European level; on the other hand, interactions with communities of researchers and projects, and especially communities of journalists and/or media are depicted. The analysis shows a greater presence in this digital social media of citizen science made in Spain compared to the other two countries of the NEWSERA consortium, Italy and Portugal. It also analyses how these two spaces interact and the accounts that play an intermediary role between the two groups. In addition, the report mentions several users and accounts not listened to by Kampal according to NEWSERA that could be taken into account when designing and preparing communication campaigns. @citscicomm is the Twitter account associated with NEWSERA, intentionally so named - citizen science communication - in order to last after the end of NEWSERA. Finally, the results and evolution of the visits obtained by the different NEWSERA videos on YouTube are presented.

Citizen and society at large

Academic Scientists

Public sector and Policy makers

Industries and SMEs

Data and science journalists

OVERVIEW

From 15 February 2022 to 10 February 2023, Kampal collected 34,701 tweets (Table 1). Three criteria were used to compile them: tweets published by the users listened to (Table 2), those that mention at least one of them and, finally, those that include one of the keywords, in this case hashtags (Table 3).

Table 1. Summary of Twitter Data

Approximate date of the first tweet	10/02/2022
Tweets from all users	34,701
Retweets from all users	55,841
Mentions between users	55,282
Answers from all users	14,774
Users	39,015
Hashtags used by all users	5,000
Approximate date of the last tweet	15/02/2023

Table 3. Keywords included in the collected tweets

Keywords	
#newsera	#citizenscience
#citscicomm	#data4citsci news
#citscijournalism	#citsci

Table 2. Users listened to by Kampal

Specified Users		
@cristinamluis	@ola_olsz	@stickydoteu
@paologiardullo	@leireleguina	@scienceed
@inavalhas	@izaskunlacunza	@llazarato
@isargantana	@cordis_eu	@anna_violato
@nadinestrauss	@datadista	@josevinas24
@karen_douglas	@mcatanzaro	@openscience_
@action4cs	@javisalas	@faustino_ai
@apassani	@vn0vais	@stickydoteu
@pmisson	@victriviac	@scienceed
@geovacui	@arago_la	@llazarato
@eucitsciproject	@storydatabcn	@anna_violato
@eucitsci	@jkeefe	@josevinas24
@citsciassoc	@sciencefchange	@openscience_
@ecsite	@formicablu	@faustino_ai
@redricap	@rosaariasalv	@citscicomm
@pcstnetwork	@jomagellan	

USERS, MENTIONS, HASHTAGS

MENTIONS

Figure 1 depicts the most mentioned users in the record generated from all the tweets collected. Among the users listened to (in blue), the most mentioned is @javisalas by far, followed in fourth and fifth places by @VictriaVic, @CORDIS_EU and @pmisson. Among the users not heard (in orange) but who still have a central role in the community, are @eldiarioes and @FECYT_Ciencia. These two are important accounts, one more institutional and the other with a journalistic dimension. The fact that they are not accounts defined by NEWSERA to be listened to by Kampal has good logic: the contents of both are very diverse and, if all the tweets they emit were collected, an excess of information would be generated that would make analysis difficult. In any case, they appear in the graph, so they are users to be taken into account.

Figure 1. Top 10 most mentioned users in the generated network of 200 users: in blue those indicated to be listened to by Kampal; in orange those not indicated.

Presence of hashtags

Out of the hashtags heard during the monitoring period, the most used were #citizenscience (7908 times in total) and #citsci (529). These two hashtags are very generic and used by many actors, so they may be of interest as a reference to contrast with the use of more specific NEWSERA hashtags.

In that sense, Figure 2 shows the evolution of #citizenscience, #citsci, in addition to the specific hashtag #data4citscinews, allowing to analyze the impact of the latter. Clearly the former has the most important use, with a very remarkable peak in October 2022 (corresponding to the ECSA Biannual Congress) and reaching a maximum of 110 uses in one day. The peak of #data4citscinews on November 28 corresponds to the day on which an event of the same name was held by the Newsera and ENJOI projects. On December 22nd the hashtag appears again, on the motive of a publication in Tercer Milenio Heraldo and the Observatory of Citizen Science in Spain. Most notably, on November 28 the hashtag #data4citscinews appears 35 times, while #citizenscience and #citsci appear 26 and 3 times, respectively.

Figure 3 presents the evolution of the usage of the other two project-specific hashtags, #newsera and #citscicomm, with a peak for #newsera on April 26, 2022, on the motive of the Engaging Citizen Science Conference in Aarhus. Both hashtags present a peak on November 28, related to the aforementioned event, as well as on November 3, when the #CitSciCommLab took place, gathering pilots from Spain in person.

Figure 2. Use of the the specific hashtag #data4citscinews, used for the relevant event, against the evolution of generical hashtags #citizenscience and #citsci.

Figure 3. Evolution of the use of the specific hashtags #newsera and #citscicomm, highlighting the peak of November 3, associated with the #CitSciCommLab, which brought together pilots from Spain on site, and that of November 28, related to the Data4CitSciNews event.

RETWEETS

Figure 4 depicts the 10 users who have achieved the highest number of retweets among the tweets collected. As can be seen, while the users that are most mentioned (Figure 1) alternate heard and unheard users, here there is a strong majority of those heard. This may be due in part to the fact that the users who get the most retweets are some such as @datadista, which offers interesting information to share as it is directly related to NEWSERA's objectives. In the case of @FECYT_Ciencia it is logical that it is less retweeted due to the huge variety of topics in its tweets, and that it gets numerous mentions as it is a partner of the NEWSERA project.

Again @javisalás is the user with the highest number of retweets, but now @datadista and @CORDIS_EU are second and third. In the sixth position of the list we find two users not listened to, @FECYT_Ciencia and @DoNASAScience.

Figure 4. Top 10 most retweeted users: in blue those indicated to be listened to by Kampal; in orange those not indicated.

TWITTER: COMMUNITIES

COMMUNITIES BY MENTIONS

Graph 1 depicts the Top 1000 most mentioned users, each of them represented by a node. At the same time, each link represents a mention from one user to another. The size of each node increases with the number of times it is mentioned by the others. When a number of nodes are highly interconnected, they are grouped into a community, which is given a certain colour. The name of the community is the name of the most mentioned node within this community. The users in the graph are not only those listened to by Kampal but all those who are linked to them through mentions and/or the hashtags defined by NEWSERA to be monitored. An explanation of the creation of communities can be given on demand.

Distribution of users by community

As can be seen in Graph 1, the main nodes of the network correspond to the users @CORDIS_EU, @javisalas and @FECYT_ES. In the upper half of the network, two communities named after the largest node stand out: CORDIS_EU, the most important, and @Karen_Douglas, the latter being very peripheral. In the central part, the communities of @FECYT_Science, @pmisson and @jomagellan stand out. The main communities in the lower part of the network are @javisalas and @eldiaroes. The account @jkeefe, corresponding to the editor of the NY Times is totally disconnected from the main network.

Graph 1. Top 1000 users grouped by communities in terms of mentions

By restricting the Graph 1 to the Top 100 users, we can more clearly observe the different members of the diverse communities. The community that occupies almost the entire upper half of the graph (Graph 2), in beige, groups users such as @CORDIS_EU, @EuCtiSci, the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), or @Ecsite, the European network of science centers and museums, i.e., these are European users predominantly related to R&I and science communication, in particular, citizen science. The lower part of this community, in the center of the entire graph, includes users related to science and citizen science, such as @citiscicomm, the account created by NEWSERA, @Odourcollect, @Ibercivis, or @FECYT_CIENCIA (the last two accounts are not listened to by Kampal but have used the hashtag #news-era and mentioned the account @citiscicomm). The account of @RosaAriasAlv (NEWSERA principal researcher), very close to @citiscicomm, NEWSERA account, and @SciencefChange, the entity that leads NEWSERA and is part of the citizen science community, occupies a central place in this large community, connecting the upper part, associated with European projects or entities, with the lower part of this community, predominantly associated with citizen science and Spanish entities in science. Italian and Portuguese researchers members of NEWSERA are also present in this community. There are not, however, any Italian accounts related to citizen science projects. This reflects two situations: on the one hand, the Italian pilots in NEWSERA have preferred, so far, working with Facebook as main digital social media, which implies legal and technical restrictions for Kampal to access the corresponding pilots data on Facebook; on the other hand, the Italian citizen science community as a whole did not have had a strong presence on Twitter, as an indicator of the very status of citizen science in Italy. In fact, the Italian Citizen Science Association just was born on February 17th of 2023, although, at the same time, there are Italian researchers in different areas with a long experience in citizen science. Regarding Portugal, also the pace of growth is not as fast as in Spain: as an illustrative situation, the Portuguese citizen science platform is currently being configured, with the impulse of Cristina Luis (FCiências.ID - Associação para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento de Ciências) and the collaboration of Francisco Sanz (Ibercivis Foundation), both NEWSERA members; in contrast, the corresponding platform in Spain has been operating since 2016, launched by Ibercivis with the collaboration of the Spanish Foundation of Science and Technology (FECYT).

4 This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and neither the European Commission nor the Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

In the central part of the graph (Graph 3), just below the big community, a smaller community stands out, in orange, with a relevant node, associated with the @jomagellan user (coordinator of NEWSERA). This community is predominantly associated with accounts related to research in Galicia and Portugal. What is noteworthy is the central role in the graph of @jomagellan, which brings together the multiple communities around NEWSERA, i.e., citizen science, science communication (lower part of the graph), and research in general in Europe. Also in this central part, we find two very important communities: @FECYT_Ciencia on the left, in dark brown, and @pmisson in bright green colour. The @pmisson account corresponds to the principal researcher of Cities at Night, NEWSERA's pilot project, with a long tradition in citizen science and a hard work in influencing policies on light pollution; that is probably why this constitutes a separate community. Its proximity to the central part of the graph shows the numerous mentions including some

of NEWSERA's hashtags which, in turn, indicate the close relationship established with this pilot, due to the alluded interests in influencing policies. Regarding the community that takes the name of FECYT_Ciencia, being this one of the NEWSERA partners - it is mainly composed of accounts associated with institutions or individuals related to research and academia.

In the lower half of the graph (Graph 4) two communities outstand: the biggest, with the main node corresponding to @javisalalas, highly recognized journalist in Spain, specialized in science, health, and technology, is related to science and technology journalism. The second one corresponding to more general journalism with users such as @eldiarioes, digital newspaper of current news on politics and economy, @VictriaVic, a journalist specialised in data and visualisation, or @datadista, a Spanish blog about data research.

Graph 2. Enlargement of the upper half of Graph 1

Graph 3. Enlargement of the central part of Graph 1

Graph 4. Enlargement of the lower half of Graph 1

TWITTER: COMMUNITIES

COMMUNITIES BY RETWEETS

Graph 5 depicts the Top 1000 most retweeted users, each of them represented by a node. At the same time, each link represents a retweet from one user to another. The size of each node increases with the number of times it is retweeted by the others. When a number of nodes are highly interconnected, they are grouped into a community, which is given a certain colour. The name of the community is the name of the most mentioned node within this community. The users in the graph are not only those listened to by Kampal but all those who are linked to them through retweets and/or the hashtags defined by NEWSERA to be monitored. An explanation of the creation of communities can be found at: http://development2.bifi.unizar.es:8000/visualization/news-era-2022/twitter_stream/communities/.

In an open science context, it is expected - from the projects themselves and from the whole community (research, funding, political, citizen) - that projects with similar themes are in contact, sharing experiences and results as much as possible, and that this is also shown in their communication actions.

Graph 5. Top 1000 users grouped by communities in terms of retweets

Graph 6 is an extension of the central part of Graph 5. What can be seen in these graphs is the relationship via retweets between the different European projects, in particular within Horizon 2020 SwafS, and user accounts associated with them. On the one hand, the community whose central node is EuCitSci (ECSA), which includes accounts from projects such as CiteSHealthEU, COESOEU, Cos4Cloud, ReinforceEU, Socio_bee, ImpetusEU, among others, stands out. On the other hand, the community with the account (listened by Kampal) SciencefChange stands out, and includes projects such as ENJOI, TRANSFORM_EU, or FEMaLeEU. The two different colors indicate that they are two communities - with retweets mainly within them - but, at the same time, the close proximity of both communities in the graph implies that there are also some interactions between them.

Graphs 7 and 8 are enlargements of the previous one, in order to show which users are represented by the main nodes.

Graph 6. Enlargement of the central part of Graph 5 outstanding the communities labelled EuCitSci and SciencefChange as well its proximity

Graph 7. Enlargement of Graph 6 highlighting the community labelled EuCitSci which includes H2020 SwafS Projects

Graph 8. Enlargement of Graph 6 highlighting the community labelled SciencefChange which includes H2020 SwafS Projects.

YouTube

The YouTube monitoring allows us to know the evolution of the different videos made by NEWSERA. Figure 5, which depicts the maximum number of visits received by each of the five videos, indicates that the video on DATA4CitSciNews obtains the highest number of visits (318), followed by The #CitiSciComm Labs - NEWSERA (163). In Figure 6 we can see the evolution of the visits over time, from the moment the video is uploaded. Moreover, it is clearly observed that the DATA4CitSciNews video achieves remarkable growth in its first month, between December 2022 and January 2023, while the rest of the videos have a progressive rise. This difference is explained in very good part if we take into account that the event corresponding to this video was co-organized by NEWSERA and by another H2020 project, ENJOI (Engagement And Journalism Innovation For Outstanding Open Science Communication), bringing this second project the participation of two more countries, The Netherlands and Belgium, together with the three of NEWSERA, Italy, Spain and Portugal) as well as two more partners dedicated to the strengthening of science participation and communication. In any case, knowing all the actions that led to this rapid increase is very relevant when launching other videos. The peaks of November 10 and 14 should be understood as errors in the record, since the graph gives the accumulated total visits at each moment, and there is no possibility of going down to lower values.

Figure 5. Number of visits received by each NEWSERA video

Figure 6. Evolution of the visits to each NEWSERA video. The DATA4CitSciNews video corresponds to the event of the same name co-organized by NEWSERA and the ENJOI H2020 project. NOTE: The peaks on November 10 and 14 are registration errors, as the graph gives the cumulative total views at each point in time.

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